

Emerging Adsorption Strategies for Textile Effluents: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract:

Controlling water contamination has grown increasingly important in recent years. During various stages of textile manufacture and processing, the textile industry produces massive amounts of complex chemical substances in the form of wastewater from underutilized components, including colors. Among the processing sectors, textile dyeing facilities generated considerable amounts of high-strength waste. Textile chemical processing generates significant volumes of wastewater containing a variety of contaminants. In recent years, researchers have placed a greater emphasis on the utilization of low-cost adsorbents for the removal of dyes and other pollutants. Activated carbon derived from natural resources is more effective at treating a wide variety of dyes. This paper examines the literature on a wide spectrum of low-cost adsorbents using contemporary research and literature.

Keywords: Activated carbon, Dye removal, low-cost adsorbents, pollutants, wastewater

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1. Introduction

With a vast and unrivaled raw material base and industrial power along the value chain, India has the largest textile industry in the world. After China, the Indian textile sector is the world's second-largest producer and exporter [1]. The Indian economy depends heavily on this industry. To engineer the necessary shape and qualities of the finished product, the textile industry uses a vast range of raw materials, equipment, and procedures. This industry's waste stream is mostly composed of water-based effluent from the several wet textile processing operations. The primary source of this effluent's production is the massive amounts of water used in chemical processing or in subsequent steps like preparation, dyeing, printing, and finishing. However, the wastewater produced by many processes is actually far more contaminated and hazardous than the standard [2]. Pollutants containing compounds that have harmful effects on microbial populations and can be harmful and carcinogenic to animals and mammals are found in dye effluents that are released uncontrolled [3]. Treating this effluent has become crucial due to the stricter regulations on industrial discharge.

2. Overview of Textile Wet Processing

Wet textile manufacturing uses a lot of water and produces a lot of effluent, which is full of all kinds of contaminants. Designing efficient wastewater treatment and pollution control techniques requires an understanding of the contaminants that emerge at each stage of processing.

2.1 Sizing

Objectives: To lessen breakage while weaving, cover warp yarns with a protective layer.

Pollutants produced include suspended particles, synthetic sizing agents, starch residues, high BOD from biodegradable starches, and perhaps leftover chemicals.

2.2 Desizing

The objective is to eliminate sizing agents so that the cloth is ready for additional treatments.

Pollutants produced include high BOD and COD, oxidizing compounds, soluble starches, enzymes (if enzymatic desizing is employed), and suspended particles.

2.3 Scouring

The objective is to eliminate processing oils and natural contaminants including waxes, lipids, and pectins.

Alkali (caustic soda), saponified fats and waxes, high pH, high BOD/COD, oil and grease, and suspended particles are among the pollutants produced.

2.4 Bleaching

The objective of bleaching is to lighten or remove the fabric's initial hue so that it may be dyed or printed.

The following pollutants were produced: oxidized organic matter, high pH, high COD, chlorinated organic compounds, and residual bleaching agents (hydrogen peroxide, chlorine compounds).

2.5 Mercerization

Enhance cotton and other cellulosic fibers' strength, luster, and dye affinity.

Pollutants produced include dissolved cellulose, sodium hydroxide residues, highly alkaline effluent, and trace amounts of organic matter.

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2.6 Dyeing

The objective is to give fibers, yarns, or textiles a consistent color.

Excess dyes, dyeing auxiliaries (salts, dispersion agents, surfactants, and wetting agents), excessive color, heavy metals, high COD/BOD, and high TDS are among the pollutants produced.

2.7 Printing

The objective is to use color in repeating, confined patterns.

Printing pastes (binders, thickeners, and solvents), pigments, unfixed dyes, wash-off chemicals, solvents, high color, and COD are among the pollutants produced.

2.8 Finishing

The objective is to provide ultimate functional or cosmetic qualities (water repellency, wrinkle resistance, and softening).

Pollutants produced include residual formaldehyde, low to moderate BOD/COD, surfactants, finishing chemicals (softeners, flame retardants, resins, fluorocarbons, silicones), and potentially hazardous organics.

2.9 Washing and Drying

The objective of washing is to remove residual chemicals and unfixed dyes or surface localized chemicals and dyes at various stages.

Pollutants generated: Mixture of all above pollutants in diluted form mainly colour, surfactants, salts, low to high COD/BOD, and thermal pollution [4].

3. Dyes in the Textile Industry: Sources, Structure, and Classification

The textile industry has employed dyes as colorants. One of the biggest challenges in wastewater treatment is dye abatement. This is due to the importance of dye treatment; dyes with an azo group are often more stable and more resistant to oxidizing chemicals, heat, and light. Because of this, they are challenging to eliminate using the majority of traditional oxidizing or biodegrading techniques. Other methods include membrane-filtration technologies (Nano-filtration, electro-dialysis, reverse osmosis, etc.), coagulation and flocculation, and photo-degradation. However, because it is expensive and has seldom been used to achieve total color removal, its application is restricted. Usually, Textile dyes are classified according to their application these are:

i. Acid Dyes: The dyes are insoluble in acid the solubility being confirmed by the presence of sulphonic acid group on dyes usually in the form of sodium salt. The acidic conditions are used for dyeing wool and nylon. The three most important classes of acid dyes in basic chemical classes are Azo, Anthraquinoid, and Triphenylmethane.

ii. Azoic Dyes: An azoic colouring matter is a water-insoluble azo compound produced in textile fibres. Azoic dyes are used for dyeing cellulosic fibres.

iii. Basic Dyes: These are amino and substituted amino compounds that are soluble in acid and become insoluble when alkali is added. They are used as dye acrylics or can be used with a mordant dye for dyeing wool and cotton.

iv. Direct Dyes: Direct dyes are inexpensive and have auxiliary chemicals associated with direct dyeing such as sodium salt, fixing agents, and metal salts. Direct dyes belong to several chemical classes like Azo, phthalocyanine, and stilbene.

v. Disperse Dyes: A dispersed dye is defined as a substantially water-insoluble having substantively for one or more hydrophobic fibres. Dyes are used on polyester, polyamide, and acrylic fibres.

vi. Fibre Reactive Dyes: Reactive dyes are coloured components capable of forming a covalent bond between the dye molecule and fibre. Fiber-reactive dyes are mainly used for cotton and cotton blends. 1.9. Mordant Dyes The term mordant dye refers to a dye, which is applied to fibre in conjunction with metallic mordant. Mordant dyes give fast, full but generally dull shades on wool and nylon.

vii. Sulphur Dyes: Sulphur dyes are used for the dyeing of cellulosic fibres in medium to deep shades of generally dull brown, black, olive, blue, green, maroon, and khaki hues.

viii. Vat Dyes: These are water-insoluble dyes, which contain at least two conjugated carbonyl groups that enable the dye to be converted into the corresponding water-soluble ionized compounds.

Several methods are employed for the treatment of textile effluents to achieve decolourization [5].

Pigments and dyes are used by the textile industry to color their goods. Because dyes are hazardous to aquatic life and degrade the aesthetics of the environment, textile businesses' discharge of wastewater containing colors into natural streams and rivers is a serious issue [6].

Table 1: Types of dyes, applications, and chemical classes

Types of dyes	Their application	Properties	Chemical classes
Acid dyes	Nylon, wool, silk, modified acrylics, paper, leather, ink-jet printing, and food	Water-soluble	Azo (including premetallized), anthraquinone, triphenylmethane, azine, xanthene, nitro, and nitroso
Basic dyes	Paper, polyacrylonitrile, modified nylons, modified polyesters, cation dyeable polyethylene terephthalate, and medicine	Water-soluble	Diazahemicyanine, triaryl methane, cyanine, hemicyanine, thiazine, oxazine, and acridine
Disperse dyes	Polyester and some amount of nylon, cellulose, cellulose acetate, and acrylic fibers	Water-insoluble and non-ionic dyes	Azo, anthraquinone, styryl, nitro, and benzo-di-furanone
Direct dyes	Cotton, rayon, paper, leather, and some amount of nylon.	Water-soluble and anionic dyes	Polyazo compounds, along with some stilbenes, phthalocyanines, and oxazines
Reactive dyes	Cotton and other cellulosic fibers and some extent wool and nylon fibers	Water-soluble	Chromophoric groups such as azo, anthraquinone, triaryl methane, phthalocyanine, formazan, and oxazine
Solvent dyes	Plastics, gasoline, lubricants, oils, and waxes	Solvent soluble while water- is insoluble and nonpolar or little polar	Predominantly azo and anthraquinone, but phthalocyanine and triaryl methane are also used
Sulfur dyes	Cotton and rayon	Water-soluble	
Vat dyes	Cotton cellulosic fibres and rayon and wool	Water-insoluble	Anthraquinone (including polycyclic quinones) and indigoids

3.1 Usage of Dyes in Industry

The initial raw material and, consequently, the finished product are colored using textile dyes. Both natural and synthetic dyes are possible. Natural colors are created using materials found in nature, whereas synthetic dyes are created scientifically using chemicals. Textiles are often dyed using a mixture of natural or synthetic colors and water. This method of efficient wet dyeing in textile production uses a significant amount of water. Plants and minerals are used to generate natural dyes, which are then mixed with seaweed and starches to ensure they adhere to the textile. Petroleum and coal tar are typically used to make synthetic colors. Because various materials need different chemicals to make the color adhere, they differ greatly.

The use of dyes results in colored water, which is problematic for the environment. Significant amounts of dyes and other chemicals are lost in the wastewater during the dyeing process. Textiles, rubber, plastics, printing, leather, cosmetics, ink, and other sectors frequently utilize dyes to color their goods. They thus produce an enormous volume of colored wastewater. Over 7 X 10⁵ tons of dye are generated annually, and there are over 10,000 commercially available dyes. An estimated 2% of dyes generated each year are released into related industries' effluents [4].

4. Overview of Wastewater Treatment Techniques

It can be difficult to remove dye compounds; many procedures are needed to bring the dye concentration down to the advised level. Understanding the types of pollutants present in textile industry wastewater, their consequences on the environment, and how to identify the different contaminants is insufficient. In order to safeguard the environment, it is crucial to comprehend and be aware of the many treatments that may be applied to these effluent discharges. This will allow the wastes to be drained into streams in a safe and acceptable manner. It is essential to protect the environment, and in order to achieve this reasonable objective, various treatments are used, and these techniques are often divided into three divisions. There have been reports of physical, chemical, and biological decolorization techniques; nevertheless, the paper and textile industries have not adopted many of these [6].

Along with membrane-filtration techniques (nanofiltration, reverse osmosis, and electrodialysis) and adsorption strategies, several physical approaches are also widely employed. The potential for membrane fouling and the necessity of periodic replacement are the main disadvantages of membrane technology. According to the extensive literature, liquid-section adsorption is one of the best techniques for removing colors from textile wastewater because it produces high-quality treated effluent when the

adsorption process is properly designed and the adsorbent is chosen. Chemical strategies include irradiation, electrochemical methods, precipitation-flocculation with Fe(II)/Ca(OH)₂, electro flotation, electro kinetic coagulation, coagulation or flocculation combined with flotation and filtration, and conventional oxidation methods using oxidizing sellers (ozone). These chemical techniques are often expensive since concentrated. Sludge accumulates and creates a disposal problem during the removal of dyes.

Since many microorganisms, including bacteria, yeasts, algae, and fungi, can accumulate and degrade specific pollutants, biological treatment methods like biodegradation techniques, which include fungal decolorization, microbial degradation, adsorption via (living or dead) microbial biomass, and bioremediation structures are commonly used

in the treatment of industrial effluents. Advanced oxidation techniques, such as photochemical oxidation techniques, are substitutes for traditional techniques. They work by producing hydroxyl radicals and other moderately reactive radicals that can break down the intractable organic materials present in textile effluent. These methods do have some serious drawbacks, though, such hefty startup and operating expenses. Using non-toxic, inexpensive, and easily accessible adsorbents, the adsorption method is a practical and effective wastewater treatment technique [7].

5. Adsorption for Dye Removal Using Low-Cost Adsorbents

A wide range of materials for adsorbent preparations is available. Generally, adsorbent raw materials are classified into three categories (a) Natural material, (b) Agricultural

Table 2: Dye Removal Methods and their Advantages and Disadvantages

Type	Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Physical	Adsorption	Good removal of a wide variety of dyes	Nonselective to adsorbate
	Membrane filtration	Remove all dye types	Concentrated sludge production
	Ion exchange	Regeneration: no adsorbent loss.	Not effective for all dyes
	Irradiation	Effective oxidation at lab scale.	Requires a lot of dissolved O ₂
	Electro kinetic coagulation	Economically feasible.	High sludge production
	Coagulation –flocculation	Good elimination of insoluble dyes	Cost of sludge treatment
	Adsorption on active carbon powder coupled with coagulation process	Matter, organic matter, and low influence on colour Fast fouling of suspended matter	Cost of active carbon powder
	RO	Retention of mineral salt and hydrolyzed reactive dyes and auxiliaries	High-pressure process, Fouling with high concentrations
	Nano filtration	Separation of mineral salts hydrolyzed reactive dyes, and auxiliaries	Treatment for the complex solution with a high concentration of pollutant
	Ultrafiltration/microfiltration	Low-pressure process	Inadequate quality for
Chemical	Fenton’s reagent	The effective decolourization of both soluble and insoluble dyes	Sludge generation
	Ozonation	Good elimination of colour	No diminution of COD values Extra costs
	Photochemical NaOCl	No sludge production was initiated and accelerates azo-bond cleavage	Formation of by-product release of aromatic amine
	Electrochemical destruction	Breakdown compounds are	High cost of electricity
Biological	Standard Biological degradation	The efficiency of the oxidizable matter is 90%	With low biodegradability of dye, the salt concentration stays constant
Photo catalysis	Post-treatment	Near-complete colour removal	For final polishing only

waste - by-products, and (c) Industrial wastes/by-products [8].

5.1 Various low-cost adsorbents' potential for dye removal: low-cost adsorption

- Natural materials: clay minerals, zeolite
- Bio-adsorbents: Fungal- Bacterial, Algal, Other biomass
- Agricultural and Industrial materials: Leaves, Seeds, Fiber, Bark, Fly ash

Several non-conventional, low-cost adsorbents have been investigated for dye removal. In particular, many adsorbents and activated carbons prepared from various waste materials have been explored for this purpose. Examples include Examples include date stones [9], jackfruit peel [10], banana peels [11], orange peels [12], garlic peel [13], corn cobs [14], rice husk [15], sawdust [16], pomegranate peel [17], bael shell [18], lemongrass leaves [19], bamboo [20], neem leaves [21], coconut shell [22], and papaya seeds [6], among others.

5.2 Reviews on dye removal using agricultural waste

Numerous academics and scientists have worked on dye removal. A synopsis of the various researchers' work is provided. Every researcher's investigation was predicated on physicochemical parameters that were modified to examine the adsorption phenomena, including solution pH, dye concentration, and contact duration.

The potential of garlic peel, an agricultural by-product, as an inexpensive adsorbent for the removal of methylene blue (MB) from aqueous solutions was assessed [13]. Contact time, starting dye concentration (25–200 mg/L), pH (4–12), and temperature (303–323 K) were evaluated in batch studies. With monolayer adsorption capacities of 82.64, 123.45, and 142.86 mg/g at 303, 313, and 323 K, respectively, the adsorption results most closely matched the Freundlich isotherm model, suggesting that the adsorption process was endothermic.

The potential application of bael shell carbon (BSC) as an adsorbent for the elimination of congo red (CR) dye from an aqueous solution was examined [18]. Numerous operational factors, including temperature, pH, contact duration, and dye concentration, were examined for their effects. First-order reversible kinetics, pseudo-first-order kinetics, and pseudo-second-order kinetics were used to represent the adsorption kinetics. At pH 5.7, 7, and 8, the dye absorption process followed the pseudo-second-order kinetic expression, whereas at pH 9, the pseudo-first-order kinetic model suited the data well. Adsorption equilibrium data were fitted using the adsorption models of Langmuir, Freundlich, and Temkin.

There was an investigation on microwave-assisted pyrolysis of corncobs and it was found to be a very a useful adsorbent for removing methylene blue, a cationic dye, from aqueous solutions [14]. Using scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), the surface properties of microwave-assisted corncobs (MACC) were examined. To forecast the ideal circumstances, the effects of a number of experimental factors were examined, including temperature, adsorbent dosage, solution pH, contact time, and starting MB dye concentration. The various isotherm and kinetic models were used to assess the adsorption equilibrium and adsorption rate data. The isotherm results demonstrated that the Freundlich model yields favorable outcomes for the equilibrium data under study.

A research was conducted to determine how well lemongrass leaf-based activated carbon (LGLAC), which was made utilizing physicochemical techniques, removed Methylene Blue dye from aqueous solutions. pH 12 was found to have the best proportion of methyl red dye eliminated. Thermodynamic parameters were assessed, such as Gibbs free energy change (G0), enthalpy change (H0), and entropy change (S0). The mechanism works on the basis of physisorption, and the adsorption process was endothermic [19].

Orthophosphoric acid was used to turn pomegranate peel into activated carbon. Methylene Blue dye (MB) adsorption from an aqueous solution was done in batch mode. At pH 8, a dosage of 0.25 g/100 mL for 120 minutes of contact time resulted in excellent removal efficiency (above 92%). The Langmuir isotherm is preferred by MB dye molecules at the qmax value of 14.03 mg/g [17].

Table 3: The removal of dyes from aqueous solution using various agricultural low-cost adsorbents

Adsorbents	Adsorbates (Dyes)	Adsorption capacity (mg/g)	Reference
Date stones	cationic and anionic	3.1-7.1 mg.g-1)	[9]
Rice Husk	Methylene blue	476.2	[15]
Bamboo	Methylene blue	67.46	[20]
Lemongrass leaf	Methylene blue	342.9	[19]
Orange peel	Congo Red	11.919	[12]
Neem Leaves	Coomassie violet	39.64	[21]
Jackfruit peel	remazol brilliant blue R	196.05	[10]
Papaya Seeds	Procion Red	73.26	[6]
Banana peel and sugarcane bagasse	Eurozol Navy Blue	32.46, and 27.54	[11]
Garlic peel	Methylene blue	142.86	[13]
Coconut shell	Malachite green)	32.683	[22]

6. Adsorption Principles and Isotherm Models

The material upon whose surface the adsorption takes place is called an adsorbent. Most activated carbon is used as an adsorbent.

Adsorption Principles: The mass transfer and adsorption of a molecule from a liquid or gas onto a solid surface is the fundamental idea behind carbon adsorption. The process used to make activated carbon results in very porous carbon particles with a huge interior surface area. Metals, inorganic molecules, and organic molecules are all drawn to and retained by this porous structure. The following factors contribute to adsorption: i) the contamination is poorly soluble in the waste; ii) the contaminant has a stronger affinity for the carbon than for the trash; and iii) a combination of the two Granular activated carbon (GAC), which is utilized in packed beds, and powdered activated carbon are the two most widely employed carbon adsorption techniques. The activated carbon adsorption process is one of the most applied technologies for the removal of trace organic compounds from an aqueous solution.

Methodology: Batch Flow System: A certain amount of carbon is continually combined with a predetermined volume of wastewater in batch-type contact operation until the pollutant in that solution has been reduced to the required level. After that, the carbon is taken out and either disposed of or recycled for future use. Typically, these procedures are only able to treat a modest amount of wastewater.

Column Flow System: Because adsorption rates are based on the solute concentration in the solution being treated, this method seems to have a number of benefits over batch operation. The carbon is constantly in touch with a new solution in order for the column to function. It is possible to put the solid adsorbent at the top of the column and drain the wasted adsorbent from the bottom.

Adsorption Isotherm: The adsorption process is studied through graphs known as adsorption isotherm.

Freundlich Isotherm: A curve that connects the concentration of a solute on the surface of an adsorbent to the concentration of the solute in the liquid it comes into contact with is known as the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. The isothermal variation of adsorption of a quantity of gas adsorbed by unit mass of solid adsorbent with pressure was empirically stated in this work. The Freundlich Adsorption equation or Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm is the name given for this equation.

The Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm is mathematically expressed as;

$$x/m = Kp^{1/n} \log(x/m) = \log K + (1/n) \log p \text{ or}$$

$$x/m = K C^{1/n} \text{ -----(1)}$$

$$\text{It is also written as } \log(x/m) = \log K + (1/n) \log C \text{ -----(2)}$$

Where, x = mass of adsorbate

m = mass of adsorbent

p = Equilibrium pressure of the adsorbate

C = Equilibrium concentration of adsorbate in solution.

K and n are constants for a given adsorbate and adsorbent at a particular temperature.

The amount of adsorption is independent of pressure at high pressure since $1/n = 0$, but it becomes dependent on pressure at high pressure. The Freundlich adsorption isotherm has some drawbacks. In an experiment called Langmuir Isotherm, Irving Langmuir released a new model [23]. The Freundlich adsorption isotherm has some drawbacks. He kept the word "isotherm" for gases adsorbed on solids. A suggested kinetic process is the source of this semi-empirical isotherm between the gas phase and the surface, it adsorbs.

The novel model isotherm for gases adsorbed to solids, published by Irving Langmuir was named after him. A suggested kinetic process is the source of this semi-empirical isotherm. It forms a monolayer: adsorbate molecules only deposit on the adsorbent's free surface, not on other adsorbate molecules that have previously been adsorbed. Langmuir developed an equation based on his theory that clarified the connection between pressure and the quantity of active sites on the surface that are undergoing adsorption.

$$\theta = KP/1+KP \text{ -----(3)}$$

Where,

θ - the number of sites on the surface that are covered with a gaseous molecule,

P - pressure and K - is the equilibrium constant for the distribution of and importance of adsorption and related domains in nature [23, 24].

7. Factors Affecting Adsorption Efficiency

The adsorption of dye can be influenced by variables such as pH, starting dye concentration, contact duration, and adsorbent dose. Here, we address these operational parameter parameters that have an impact on the adsorption process as reported by different studies.

7.1 Effect of pH

Because of the exchange inside the ionization stage and the adsorbents' surface price, a change in pH affects the reaction between dye molecules and adsorbents. The presence of various types of salts (primary and acidic) may also affect the dye effluent's pH.

For instance, how the initial pH affects the MB adsorption equilibrium when employing date stone activated carbon [9]. Variations in pH had an impact on how much dye was removed by activated carbon. Even though the dye removal

percentage for ionic dye adsorption increases at low pH, the dye elimination percentage for cationic dye often decreases.

7.2 Effect of adsorbent dose

One of the most important factors in determining the adsorbent's capacity to absorb a specific amount of adsorbate in operational conditions is the adsorbent dosage. An increase in dosage often results in more active sites, which raises the adsorption capacity. A large dosage has an impact on treatment economy and is strongly correlated with the quantity of active sites on the adsorbent's surface. A large dosage, however, congests active areas. For instance, when the amount of the biosorbent was raised from 0.15 to 0.25 g/100 mL, the removal percentage rose from 93.38% to 95.70% utilizing activated carbon from pomegranate peel [17].

7.3 Effect of initial concentration

The initial dye concentration of effluent is one of the crucial criteria to be examined since a certain amount of sorbent material can only adsorb a set quantity of dye. Shaken adsorbent-adsorbate till equilibrium condition may be used to obtain the effect of varying starting dye concentrations over varying time periods utilizing fixed adsorbent dose [19].

7.4 Effect of temperature

The endothermic character of reactions is shown by the adsorption potential increasing with temperature, whereas the exothermic nature of processes is suggested by a reduction in adsorption capacity increasing with temperature. A rise in temperature improves the adsorption capacity in the fashion industry, but a greater temperature is unacceptable. For example. When the solution's temperature was raised from 303 to 323 K, the adsorption capacity rose from 82.64 to 142.86 mg/g, suggesting that the process of batch adsorption of methylene blue from aqueous solution using garlic peel as an adsorbent is endothermic [13].

7.5 Effect of reaction time

It is the amount of time when the adsorbent and adsorbate are in contact. As contact duration increases, adsorbent and dye

molecules' active sites are created. The economics of the treatment procedures is impacted by high reaction times since they raise energy needs. with example, the amount of dye (BR29) adsorbed over time at various beginning concentrations using neem leaf activated carbon with an initial dye concentration of 50 mg/L and pH of 8.54 [21].

8. Summary and future scope

In the future, the textile industry's sustainable wastewater management might be completely transformed by including adsorbents made from agro-waste into textile effluent treatment. These inexpensive, renewable resources, which are converted into high-performance activated carbon, show remarkable dye removal effectiveness under a range of operating circumstances, providing a reliable and environmentally responsible substitute for traditional adsorbents.

Valorising agricultural residues for pollutant adsorption is in line with global sustainability goals as sectors transition to circular economy models, reducing waste production while optimizing resource use and cost-effectiveness. It is anticipated that future developments will concentrate on expanding these adsorption systems, refining regeneration methods, and carrying out thorough techno-economic and life cycle analyses to guarantee their feasibility on an industrial scale. Agro-waste-based adsorption technologies have the potential to be a key component in reaching zero liquid discharge targets and promoting cleaner, more environmentally friendly textile production methods globally, provided that they get ongoing innovation and regulatory support. In addition to protecting water supplies, this paradigm change will turn agricultural waste into useful resources for environmental cleanup, propelling industry toward a more resilient and sustainable future.

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